

ANOTOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A YOUNG PERSON OF A SMALL SCHOOL**Irmatova Mamura Juraevna**

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Abstract. *In the proverb, the anatomical and physiological development of development at a small school age is reduced in its own way, successful schooling depends not only on its mental and physical training, but also on personal , socio-psychological training, the child coming to study has a new social status-with different obligations and rights, and various requirements are imposed*

Keywords: *organism, development, nervous system, ability, giving, organism, attention, thinking, behavior.*

АНОТОМИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ РЕБЕНКА МЛАДШЕЙ ШКОЛЫ.

Аннотация. *В пословице анатомо-физиологическое развитие в младшем школьном возрасте сводится по-своему, успешное школьное обучение зависит не только от его умственной и физической подготовки, но и от личностной, социально-психологической подготовки, будущего ребенка. учиться имеет новый социальный статус – с другими обязанностями и правами, предъявляются различные требования.*

Ключевые слова: *организм, развитие, нервная система, способности, отдача, организм, внимание, мышление, поведение.*

Educational activities are not only knowledge for a high school student. the high level of development of the process, but also the possibility of developing individual characteristics. At a small school age, the formation of the child's personality continues. Student's success in school is a completely positive basis for his further mental development and personality formation. This is as a result of the child's own family, his class, etc. it is clear that he began to understand his place in the teams. The transition to a new activity is the new main activity of the student. creates relationships.

In it, a sense of duty begins to grow. It understands that it is a duty to read, that the established rules and requirements must be met. The child must first be physically ready for school.

The anatomical and physiological development of 6-year-old children proceeds in a special way. At this age, the child's organism develops rapidly. Its weight increases from 150 to 200 per month, and its height increases to 0.5 cm. 6-year-olds can run at different speeds, fast and light.

They can also freely perform movements such as jumping, skating, skiing, swimming. In music training, however, they perform a variety of rhythmic and plastic movements, being able to perform a variety of exercises accurately, quickly, lightly and dexterously. Children 6-7 years old are extremely important, strengthening the nervous system, relieving them of chronic diseases, paying special attention to vision and hearing, as well as paying attention to the correct development of the spine. Since adults work with children of this age, it is necessary to constantly take into account that the organism of children of this age is still growing. For example, teaching a child to write forcibly can harm them to a certain extent due to the fact that the finger muscles are not yet fully developed, and the child's inability to write beautifully can, in itself, lead to a decrease in the child's self-confidence or interest in reading. Successful schooling of a child depends not only on his mental and physical training, but also on his personal, socio-psychological training. Students of small school age will have the property of being able to easily tell the negative characteristics of their comrade between many and strangers.

This can cause a child who is being criticized in terms of morality and etiquette to refuse to join their fellow community or not want to come to school at all. This reason is considered no less moral preparation in terms of the importance of teaching a child to the rules of etiquette so that he is not subject to criticism by his comrades and mentors. The volitional preparation of the child for school will help him to follow a new agenda, diligently assimilate knowledge in the course of the lesson, perform homework. The child coming to school must be ready to receive the status of a student — having a new social status — various obligations and rights, and various requirements are imposed on him. This desire and effort will naturally take the basis for the child to successfully study at school.

It is extremely important for the child to realize that he is now older, that he is not a kindergarten child, but a student with certain obligations, that he is engaged in serious activities.

The fact that a child does not want to go to school is also a negative condition. Personal and socio-psychological preparation for school also involves the formation of the character of being able to enter into relationships with peers, teachers in children. It is necessary that each child can join the children's team, act in cooperation with them, be able to achieve side-clicking on them in some situations and not side-clicking in other situations. These characteristics ensure that the child can quickly adapt to new conditions at school. The main difficulty in the study of children 6-7 years old is that often children of this age cannot listen to the teacher for a long time, cannot focus on educational actions for a long time. The reason for this lies not only in the underdevelopment of voluntary attention in children of this age, but also in the nature of the child's ability to enter into communication with adults.

Because, children with this characteristic development will be able to enter into free communication, ask about what is of interest. As a result, their interest in studying increases, and the teacher is able to hear what he is talking about carefully for a long time. Therefore, the importance of both personal and socio-psychological training in the rapid adaptation and successful study of the child to school is very great. During this period, children begin to have an inner personal life, first in the areas of cognition, and then in the direction of emotional motivation.

Development in one direction or another takes stages that range from figurative to symbolic. When it is called figurativeness, it is understood that children create different images, change them and move freely, and when it is called symbolism, the skill of working with a system of symbols (mathematical, linguistic, logical, etc.) is understood. In the preschool age period, the process of Creativity Begins. Creativity is manifested mainly in children's design Games, technical and artistic creations. During this period, the primary development of buds of special abilities begins to be visible. In the preschool period, imagination, thinking and speech generalize. This is evidenced by the fact that internal speech occurs as a factor of thinking in children of this age. The synthesis of cognitive processes lies on the basis of the complete occupation of the child's own native language. During this period, the process of formation of speech begins to complete. In the process of speech-based upbringing, the child acquires simple moral standards and rules. These norms and rules govern the morality of the child. The junior school period lasts from 6-7 to 9-10 years. His psyche develops to the point where it reaches knowledge. One of the important features of a small school-age child is the presence of specific needs in it. These needs, in their essence, consist not only in the acquisition of certain knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also in the reflection of the desire to study. Based on these needs, the child has his own portfolio, personal educational tools, a lesson preparation table, a bookshelf, a desire to go to school every day as an adult. This need is considered of great importance in the formation of the child's personality, as well as in its socialization. During this period, the child will be biologically and psychologically ready to learn the basics of science. According to physiologists, by the age of 7 the child's large cerebral hemispheres will be developed to some extent. But at this age, the special compartments of the human brain that respond to such complex forms of mental activity as planning, control, control are still complete it will not be formed (these parts of the brain will develop at the age of 12).

The failure to fully form the control functions of the brain is evident in the Behavior, Organization of activities and emotional spheres of children of small school age. Some 6-year-olds step on the threshold of the school, not yet ready to study at the discretion of their parents.

Unfortunately, as a result of mental-mental strain during study, various diseases are acquired, defects in physical and mental development appear. In such children, first of all, it is observed that the structure of the brain and the mental processes of the nerve are not enough to study at school, there is an underdevelopment of visual motor coordination and small motorics, and there is a low productivity of logical thinking. Beyond that motivation, volitional aspects of volitional especially non-formation of volitional attention and memory, problems in voluntary management of behavior, in a word not yet formed a "growing inner position" negatively affect the successful assimilation of children who are not ready to study at school. Educators should also pay special attention to the neurophysiological laws of human brain development when they think about the benefits or harms of giving children to early school. By teaching the child to read, write, count early, his cognitive processes are strained, it becomes the reason for the shortage of brain power necessary for the emotional development of the child. From this, deficiencies occur in the course or physical development of emotional processes of children. In this case, a forced violation of energy distribution occurs, which leads children 7-8 years old to cases of fear, aggressiveness or hyperactivity. This is not an opinion that it is not necessary to prepare a child for schooling, but the mental development of a child cannot be achieved only if he can be taught to read, count, write early. As you know, kola to the law of development, any progress goes from visual imagery to abstract logic. If a child is not yet mentally, spiritually-mentally ready to study, writing letters and numbers to him, reading will be the reason why psychic development will go the opposite way. According to psychologist scientists, the laws of development of the psyche and evolution are not as violated as physical laws, and are universal. Summarizing the above points, it can be said that many brain processes that are necessary for neurophysiologically voluntary attention and Reading are formed mainly at the age of 7-8 years (even at the age of six in children whose mental age is exceeded). That is, at this age, the child will be ready for 45 minutes of mental work. The onset of schooling is consistent with the fourth physiological crisis, which occurs at the age of 7 years (a sharp endocrine change occurs in the child's body associated with accelerated growth of height, enlargement of internal organs, vegetative changes). A 6-7 year old school-ready child begins to be dominated by the "that's what I want" motif from the "that's what I have to do" motif. In every student who comes to first grade at school, psychic tension increases. This is manifested not only in his physical health, but also in his behavior, for example, to a certain extent, increased fear, decreased volitional activity. Cardinal changes in the system and activity of a child's social relations presuppose the need for strong tension and full use of one's own internal capabilities from a child in accordance with changes in all systems and functions in his body. These changes in a child who is ready for school do not bring negative consequences, but rather contribute to his

successful adaptation to new conditions. the attitude style of the teacher directly affects the activity of the student. Children of small school age are quickly distracted, cannot focus their attention on one thing for a long time, become impressionable and emotional children. There are basically three different manifestations of student activity at a small school age, these are: physical, psychic and social activity. Physical activity-soglom is natural in overcoming the various existing obstacles that the body has to move it is necessary.

Children of this age are extremely productive. This physical act is also associated with the fact that the child is interested in the surrounding objects, striving to learn them. The physical and psychic activity of the child is mutual. Because, a psychic sog'lom child will be mobile, and a tired, compressed child will be interested in almost nothing. Psychic activity is the interest of a normally developing child in relation to the knowledge of objects, human relationships in the surrounding world. Psychic activity is also understood as the child's need for self-knowledge. A number of difficulties arise in a child who first comes to school. It is difficult for them, first of all, to obey a number of school rules. The most difficult rule for a primary student is to sit quietly during class time.

Teachers try to keep students sitting quietly all the time, but only a low-mobility, passive, underpowered student can sit quietly for a long time during the course of the lesson.

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